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Vinnytsia National Technical University
P.N. Platonov Institute of Computer Engineering, Automation,
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робототехніки та програмування ім.П.Н.Платонова**

**«ІНФОРМАЦІЙНІ ТЕХНОЛОГІЇ І
АВТОМАТИЗАЦІЯ – 2024»**

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Інформаційні технології і автоматизація – 2024 / Матеріали XVII міжнародної науково-практичної конференції. Одеса, 31 жовтня - 1 листопада 2024 р. - Одеса, Видавництво ОНТУ, 2024 р. – 847 с.

Збірник включає матеріали доповідей учасників конференції, які об'єднані за тематичними напрямками конференції.

Збірник буде корисним як для фахівців і працівників фірм, зайнятих в області ІТ та автоматизації, так і для викладачів, магістрів і студентів вищих навчальних закладів, які навчаються за напрямками і спеціальностями програмного забезпечення, обчислювальної техніки і автоматизованих систем, прикладної математики та обробки інформації, буде корисним професіоналам з комп'ютерного моделювання та розробки комп'ютерних ігор.

Результати досліджень у збірнику представляють собою своєрідний зріз сучасного стану справ в перерахованих галузях знань, який може допомогти як фахівцям, так і студентам університетів скласти загальну картину розвитку інформаційних технологій та пов'язаних з ними питань.

Наукові праці згруповані за напрямками роботи конференції та наведені в алфавітному порядку прізвищ авторів.

Матеріали (тези доповідей) друкуються в авторській редакції. Відповідальність за якість та зміст публікацій несе автор.

Матеріали подано українською та англійською мовами.

Головний редактор збірника Сергій Котлик

Information Technologies and Automation - 2024 / Proceedings of the XVII International Scientific and Practical Conference. Odessa, October 31 - November 1, 2024. - Odessa, ONUT Publishing House, 2024 – 847 p.

The collection includes materials of reports of conference participants, which are united by thematic areas of the conference.

The collection will be useful for professionals and employees of companies engaged in the field of IT, as well as for teachers, masters and students of higher education institutions studying in the areas and specialties of computer software and automated systems, applied mathematics and information processing, will be useful to professionals on computer modeling and development of computer games.

The results of research in the collection are a kind of slice of the current state of affairs in these areas of knowledge, which can help both professionals and university students to get a general picture of the development of information technology and related issues.

Scientific papers are grouped by areas of the conference and are listed in alphabetical order of the authors.

Materials (abstracts) are published in the author's edition. The author is responsible for the quality and content of publications.

Materials are submitted in Ukrainian and English.
Editor-in-Chief of the collection Sergii Kotlyk.

Parameters	“Fortnite”	“Fallout 76”
Navigation	Clean and Responsive Interface	Clunky Interface
Consistency	Adaptive and Responsive Design	Inconsistent UI
Responsiveness	Interactive Feedback and User-Centric Design	Lack of Responsive Design

Table 1 – The comparison results of games’ design

Good web design, as seen in “Fortnite”, significantly enhances the player’s experience by making the interface intuitive, responsive, and engaging, while poor web design, as seen in “Fallout 76”, can detract from the overall enjoyment of the game.

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RECOMMENDATIONS FOR USING OF EXERGAME TECHNOLOGIES FOR BALANCE BOARDS IN DIFFERENT HARDWARE/SOFTWARE CONFIGURATIONS

Volkov A.S., Blazhko O.A. (asanvolkov20@gmail.com, blazhko@op.edu.ua)
 Odesa Polytechnic National University, Ukraine

Abstract. The paper provides a list of recommendations for the use of Exergame technologies for Rocker and Wobble class balance boards based on different hardware and software options using the Mechanics-Dynamics-Aesthetics model in the process of performing physical exercises for legs, arms, and hips

Introduction. Maintaining balance is a basic sensorimotor ability of a person, so it is important to conduct regular balance therapy, which is based on internal motivation to learn without the supervision of a therapist or through the support of a virtual therapist based on specialized computer programs using, for example, balance boards [1]. Most balance boards can be divided into four classes [2]: Rocker board - a bipolar board with a fixed sphere with the ability to move the center of gravity of the human body in two directions (left/right or forward/backward); Wobble board - a multipolar board with a fixed sphere for moving the center of gravity of the body 360 degrees; Roller board - a bipolar board with a non-fixed sphere with an additional possibility of movement in two directions; Sphere-and-ring board - a multipolar board with a non-fixed sphere. The analysis of the reviewed papers identified the following open issues: no comparative analysis of balance boards for character control in games, lack of analysis of technical aspects in game-board interactions, no analysis of variants of mechanics implementation implemented in computer games, no recommendations for new exercises linking muscle engagement and game mechanics. Therefore, the purpose of this paper is to determine recommendations for the use of Exergame technologies for Rocker/Wobble balance boards based on various hardware and software options using the Mechanics-Dynamics-Aesthetics model in the process of performing physical exercises for the legs, arms, and hips. (Figure 1).

Figure 1: ExerGame-components with balance boards

The main part of the work. To conduct a comparative analysis of physical exercises on Rocker/Wobble boards, physical exercises from the booklets of Si Boards, CoolBoard, and CanDo Balance Boards were used. Figure 2 shows the exercises of the booklets and the muscles most affected by the exercises. For exercises № 1-2 - muscle № 14; exercise № 3 - muscles № 10, 14; exercise № 4 - muscle № 10; for exercises № 5, 8 - muscle № 5; exercise № 6-7 - muscles № 4, 6; exercises № 9-10 - muscles № 1-3; exercise № 11 - muscles № 4-5; exercise № 12 - muscles № 4-9, № 11-13.

Figure 2: Exercises of the booklets and the muscles most affected by the exercises

The experiments revealed the following:

- 12 exercises for 3th groups: standing - 33%, handstand - 50%, lying down - 17%;
- statistical analysis of the use of muscle groups determined that the exercises most often involve muscles № 4-6, № 10, № 14;
- the muscles № 10, № 14 are responsible for movement in all directions, muscles № 1-6, № 10 are responsible for movement to the left/right; muscles № 4-9, № 11-13 are responsible for forward/backward movement;
- correlation analysis (CA) of the relationship between groups of exercises and the direction of gaze of the eyes during the exercises, that for standing on the legs the gaze has a horizontal direction, for handstands it is horizontal-vertical with a lower angle of inclination, in lying position – the gaze is vertical with an upper angle;
- CA of the relationship between physical exercise groups and the convenience of looking at the trainer (screen) during the exercise on the scale "convenient", "partially convenient", and "inconvenient" determined that standing on the feet is convenient, handstand and lying down are partially convenient for looking at the screen;
- performing movements on the Wobble board is more difficult than on the Rocker board.

To conduct the experiments, we used the Plankpad system [3] with smartphone-type hardware technologies that provides free access to testing games on a balance board. In this work was created an experimental Rocker/Wooble boards. To test hardware technology it was created nine computer games with properties: (1) Arduino Nano microcontroller and MPU6050 module with gyroscope/accelerometer sensors, (2) sensors on the bottom of the board surface, (3) the Arduino Nano software was created in C

to transmit signals from the sensors to the computer OS, (4) computer games are created in the Scratch for Arduino (S4F) program of block visual programming.

Figure 3 shows screenshots of the computer games developed by the authors: (1) "Bat"; (2) "Krabik"; (3) "Space Tennis"; (4) "Bird"; (5) "Skier"; (6) "Car"; (7) "Magic Hats", (8) "Fire Attack" and "Labyrinth" (9).

Figure 3: Screenshots of computer games developed by the authors for the experiments

The following features were used for the comparative analysis of Smartphone/Microcontroller games (S/M G): technical features (directions of movements on the board, group of exercises (for hips, arms, legs), board class), game features (the speed ratio of the protagonist's to the antagonist's (median), frequency of appearance of game characters (median), ratio of game characters' strengths (median), complexity level (median), control type, aesthetics from the MDA model, methods of evaluating the user's performance. To analyze the "Aesthetics" component of the MDA model, we used the following types of aesthetics [4]: (1) Sensation, (2) Fantasy, (3) Narrative, (4) Challenge, (5) Fellowship, (6) Discovery, (7) Expression, (8) Submission. Smartphone games have multiple game modes: Easy (E), Normal (N), Hard (H), and Arcade (A).

The comparative analysis of the results revealed the following:

- directions of movements on the board: SG use left-right directions, and MG use all directions;
- exercise groups (for hips, arms, legs): for SG, standing, and handstand are used, and for MG, standing, handstand, and lying down are used;
- board classes: for SG a Rocker board is used, for MG a Rocker/Wobble board is used;
- the speed ratio of the protagonist to the antagonists (median): for SG is 0.29 (E), 0.33 (N/A), 0.5 (H), for MG the median is 1;
- the frequency of appearance of game characters (median): for SG is 1 second between appearances (E), 1.25 seconds between appearances (N/A), 0.25 seconds between appearances (H), for MG the median is 0 seconds between appearances;
- the ratio of game characters' strengths (median): for SG is 3, for MG the median is 1;
- complexity level (median): for SG is 2 (E), 3 (N), 5 (A), 4 (H), for MG the median is 5;
- the control type: all SG use coordinate control as the control type, and MG use coordinate control in games №1, №5, and MG №2-4, №6-9 use angular tilt;
- aesthetics from the MDA model: all SG have aesthetic types 1-2, SG “Meteor Madness” (game modes: H/A), “Duck Shoot” (game mode: A), “Snow Cruisin” (game modes: H/A), “Pong Goal” (game mode: A) have aesthetic type 4, all MG have aesthetic types 1-2, MG №4, №6, №8-9 have aesthetic type 4, MG №9 has aesthetic type 6;
- the methods of evaluating the user's result: for all SG, points/play time is the method of evaluating the user's result, for MG, counting the time of the game until its end (6 times in games №2-3, №5-6, №8-9), counting points until the end of the game (2 times – in games №4, №7), points/play time (once – in game №1) are the methods of evaluating the result.

Conclusions. The paper provides a list of recommendations for the use of Exergame technologies for Rocker and Wobble class balance boards based on different hardware and software options using the Mechanics-Dynamics-Aesthetics model in the process of performing physical exercises for legs, arms, and hips.

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COMPUTER GAMES AND WEB DESIGN

Andreiev A. S., Sotnik S.V.

(pavlo.sukhno@nure.ua, svetlana.sotnik @nure.ua)

Kharkiv National University of Radio Electronics (Ukraine)

The article explores integration of computer game elements into Web design, focusing on impact of gamification on user experience and engagement. Key aspects such as advantages and challenges of this innovative approach are examined. Particular attention is paid to processes of implementing game mechanics and dynamics in Web interfaces, which aim to enhance user interaction and information retention. Analysis of user behavior in gamified Web environments demonstrates how adaptive design can improve overall Website effectiveness. The results of study confirm relevance of gamification in various digital contexts, emphasizing its importance in meeting evolving expectations of modern users. The identified benefits and potential drawbacks of gamification in Web design provide insights for optimizing user interfaces, potentially increasing user satisfaction and loyalty. These findings also serve as foundation for further research in field of user-centered design, ensuring competitiveness in rapidly evolving digital landscape. The study highlights need for balanced approach to gamification, considering ethical implications and accessibility concerns, to create Web experiences that are both engaging and inclusive.

Problem Statement.

The integration of computer game elements into Web design described in this paper reflects broader trends in automation, robotization, and informatization in digital environment. Automation is manifested in self-adaptive systems that adapt to user actions, using dynamic content and personalization to optimize interaction [1 - 4]. Informatization is realized through gamification, which contributes to more effective learning and memorization of content, as well as through innovative approaches to presentation of information [5, 6]. Elements of robotics are present in adaptive design, which automatically adjusts interface to different devices and usage scenarios [7, 8]. Integration of social features and automated analysis of user behavior also play important role in modern Web design. All these aspects together create more efficient, intuitive, and attractive Web interfaces that meet expectations of modern users and demonstrate how automation, robotization, and informatization are becoming integral parts of digital design.

In today's world, where digital technologies have become integral part of life, young people actively use smartphones, spend time on internet, and enjoy music online. For this generation, boundary between virtual and real worlds is becoming increasingly blurred, as they are constantly connected.

Designing interfaces in this context becomes complex task with many methodological challenges. Designers must not only adhere to basic principles of human-computer interaction but also integrate them with information and communication technology concepts that support social interaction. It is important to consider perceptual characteristics of young generation that has grown up in digital environment.